

The Effect of Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction at St. Joseph Referral Hospital-Peramiho, Tanzania

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Abstract:

This study was carried out to assess the effect of service quality on customer satisfaction in health sector. The specific objectives of the study were to examine the effect of tangibility as a service quality dimension on customer satisfaction at St. Joseph referral hospital-Peramiho, to find out the effect of reliability as a service quality dimension on customer satisfaction at St. Joseph referral hospital-Peramiho, to examine the effect of responsiveness as a service quality dimension on customer satisfaction at St. Joseph referral hospital-Peramiho, to examine the effect of assurance as a service quality dimension on customer satisfaction at St. Joseph referral hospital-

Peramiho and to examine the effect of empathy as a service quality dimension on customer satisfaction at St. Joseph referral hospital-Peramiho. The study used simple random sampling to select 123 respondents whereas data were solicited through questionnaire. Data were analysed using Structural equation model (SEM). The study found that tangibility has significant effect on customers' satisfaction at St. Joseph referral hospital-Peramiho. The tangible elements of a healthcare service include the physical facilities, equipment, and appearance of healthcare professionals. The study also found that service quality reliability has significant effect on customers' satisfaction. Likewise, the study indicated that service quality responsiveness has significant effect on customers' satisfaction. Health services at St. Joseph referral hospital-Peramiho are unique in that they often involve people seeking assistance during times of vulnerability, uncertainty, and distress. The study concluded that all attributes have strong and positive associations with their respective observed items. The study recommended that the management of hospital should continue enhance these attributes of service quality so as to continue satisfying the customers who are the patients.

Keywords: *Service Quality, Customer Satisfaction, St. Joseph Referral Hospital-Peramiho.*

Introduction

The world is changing at a breakneck pace, and human demands are growing by the day. Health is growing increasingly vital and has become one of the most basic human needs, which was previously disregarded. The health sector is the most important service sector in many countries

since it is critical to preserving and enhancing public health in order to achieve a country's objectives (Lasadika, 2018). In today's competitive economy, The United States of America (USA), the United Kingdom (UK), Germany, France, South Korea, and China are developed countries. Customer satisfaction has

emerged as a critical predictor of long-term performance and survival in the health business (Laohasrichaikul *et al*, 2017). Service quality, on the other hand, has become a key focus in the service business in terms of delighting and maintaining clients (Spreng & MacKoy, 2016). As a result, one of the most important measures of client satisfaction is service quality, and assessing it can help you learn more about a company's operations, especially in the health-care market (Aliyeva, 2015). There are various debates and arguments from various scholars on the effect of service quality on customer satisfaction. Some scholars generally agree that reliability is an important dimension of service quality in the health sector and that it has a positive impact on patient satisfaction. For example, a study by Zarei (2015) found that reliability was the most important dimension of service quality for patients in a hospital setting. On the same way some scholars agree that responsiveness is an important dimension of service quality in the health sector and that it has a positive impact on patient satisfaction. For example, a study by Asefa *et al.* (2017) found that responsiveness was the most important dimension of service quality for patients in a hospital setting.

Unlike in developed countries, where improvements in the health sector have led to higher consumer satisfaction, the majority of patients in African countries are dissatisfied with public hospital treatments. In a study conducted in Nigeria, Potluri (2018) found that the quality of public health care providers' services is often inadequate and shambolic, especially in terms of structure, organization, and duty allocation. Other drawbacks include a dingy appearance of the hospital buildings, unskilled medical personnel, and insufficient facilities. Employees in this field are frequently accused of treating patients in an unprofessional and casual manner, and they frequently vent their frustrations on the patients they are responsible for. According to Wambungu (2018), Kenya's public health system is plagued by excessive bureaucracy, political intervention, corruption, nepotism, inhospitable working conditions, and a lack of work ethics.

Patients are treated as clients by the hospital, and they expect high-quality care. The patient's satisfaction is determined by the hospital's service performance. Hospital services are essential since life is of the utmost importance. Service providers must be proactive in responding to shifting patterns of client preferences in order to survive in this dynamic environment, where consumer tastes are always changing due to easy access to and availability of information (Baia & Baptista, 2020). In an ideal situation, Peramiho Hospital would strive to provide exceptional service quality to its patients. However, in reality the hospital has been constrained with long waiting times. Due to resource constraints or inefficiencies, patients may experience long waiting times for appointments, consultations, and procedures. This leads to frustration and dissatisfaction among patients. Limited availability of healthcare professionals or insufficient staffing levels can result in compromised service quality. Overworked staff may struggle to provide the level of care and attention that patients expect, leading to lower satisfaction levels. In that regard, the gap analysis aims to identify the difference between the ideal situation and the reality situation at Peramiho Hospital regarding service quality and customer satisfaction.

Literature Review

Service quality and patient satisfaction are receiving a lot of attention in the healthcare industry and this issue is being integrated into their strategic planning process. Aside from patient loyalty and word-of-mouth, patients' perceptions of specific health-care organizations' services have an impact on the hospital's image and profitability (Andaleeb, 2015). Furthermore, rising patient expectations for service quality forced healthcare professionals to identify the major elements that contribute to patient happiness in order to improve healthcare services as well as assisting service providers in reducing the time and money spent on dealing with patient complaints (Gobah, 2015). Every town, according to the national health strategy, needs its own dispensary to give access to

medical services. However, because the resources available do not fulfill all of the needs, this has not yet been accomplished human resource training and development has not been done in accordance with the actual needs and demands of community members. Surprisingly, easily available medical facilities have been unable to provide full care (Karinga, 2015).

This study adopted SERVQUAL theory. Berry and his colleagues Parasuraman and Seithamli utilised the in the mid-1980s the Perceived Service Quality concept to explore service quality attributes and client perceptions. The ten criteria were discovered to be linked to customers' perceptions of the service. Competence, for example, is obviously linked to the outcome's technical quality, whereas credibility, on the other hand, is linked to the perceived quality's image element. The remaining parts, on the other hand, are all in some way related to the perceived quality process dimension (Babakus & Mangold, 2015). The following five service quality requirements were reduced to ten after a second investigation:

Tangibles: The appeal of a service firm's facilities, equipment, and materials, as well as the appearance of its staff, all influence this quality (Zaim et al., 2010).

Reliability: This is the ability of a service provider to consistently deliver services that meet or exceed customer expectations (Zaim et al., 2010).

Responsiveness: This refers to a company's willingness to assist customers and respond to their requests, as well as to inform customers when help will be available and then provide prompt service (Akhade et al., 2016).

Assurance: Customers will have faith in the firm because of the behaviors of its personnel, and the company will make them feel safe. It also indicates that personnel are always polite and capable of dealing with consumer issues (Babakus & Mangold, 2015).

Empathy: This indicates that the company understands its clients' concerns and attempts to solve them, as well as providing personalized service and convenient hours of operation (Zaim and colleagues, 2010).

Figure 1. Measuring Service Quality Using SERVQUAL Model

Source: Parasuraman et al, 1988

In this study, the SERVQUAL model is significant since it establishes five major features for evaluating service quality in respect to the

research organization's offerings. As a result, in this study, the Servqual Model was used effectively and efficiently.

Methodology

The study adopted positivism as the philosophical approach in conducting the study. Therefore, with this phenomenon, only positive requirements to the response on the effect of service quality on customer satisfaction in health sector were applied. A cross-section design was used to the effect of service quality on customer satisfaction in health sector. This design was useful and appropriate in this study as it enabled the researcher to examine the effect of tangibility on customer satisfaction at St. Joseph Referral Hospital-Peramiho. The total population of the patients who are customers attended by St. Joseph Referral Hospital-Peramiho is 163,909. This is according to St. Joseph Referral Hospital-Peramiho report of 2021. To determine the sample size for this investigation, simple random sampling was used. The patients were collected using a simple random sample procedure. This is a sort of probability sampling in which each person in the population has an equal chance of being selected for a sample. A total of 123 of patients who are the customers of St. Joseph Referral Hospital-Peramiho was sampled. This is according to Magigi (2015) who suggested using Slovin's formula when the population is large. Therefore, the sample size of this study is determined by Slovin's formula with a confidence level of 91% and margin of error of 9% (1-0.09), the formula is expressed as hereunder;

$$n = N \div (1 + Ne^2) \quad (1)$$

Where:

n = is number of sample (required)

N = Total population (163,909) and

e = Error tolerance (level) or margin of error (0.09)

Using above formula, the sample size is calculated as indicated below;

$$163,909 / (1 + 163,909(0.09)^2) = 163,909 / 1,328.6629$$

$$= 123.3638$$

In that regard, the sample size of the study was 123 respondents.

Structural equation model (SEM) was performed to evaluate relationship between structural path. This involves the test of hypothesis where by structural equation modeling (SEM) was used. SEM was preferable for this study as it allows testing relationship whether there is one or multiple independent and dependent variables which are either continuous or discrete and can either be latent or observed variables (Ullman, 2006). This study contained multiple independent variables which are latent. Furthermore, in SEM the errors are estimated and removed. This allowed the analysis of relations which are ideally measurement error free (Ullman, 2006; Ullman and Bentler, 2013).

Findings and Discussions

Structural Equation Model (SEM) to assess the Effect of Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction in Health Sector

In Figure 1, a path diagram for the measurement model is presented, displaying factor loadings, path coefficients, and R-square values.

The path diagram illustrates the relationships between latent variables and their observed indicators in the measurement model.

Factor loadings represent the strength of the relationship between the latent variables and their corresponding observed indicators. Higher factor loadings indicate a stronger association between the underlying construct and the observed measures. Researchers use factor loadings to assess the reliability and validity of the measurement model. Significant and high factor loadings indicate that the observed indicators are good representations of the latent variables they are measuring.

Path coefficients represent the strength and direction of the relationships between the latent variables in the model. These coefficients reveal how much one latent variable influence another. Positive coefficients indicate a positive

relationship, while negative coefficients indicate a negative relationship. The magnitude of the path coefficients determines the extent to which changes in one variable affect changes in another. Researchers use path coefficients to understand the causal relationships between different latent variables.

R-square (R^2) values represent the proportion of variance in each latent variable that is explained by its observed indicators. A higher R-square indicates that the observed indicators are better at explaining the variability in the underlying construct. R-square values close to 1 indicate that the measurement model adequately represents the latent variable, while lower values

suggest that there may be other factors contributing to the construct that are not captured by the observed indicators.

In summary, the path diagram and its associated factor loadings, path coefficients, and R-square values provide valuable information about the measurement model's validity and explanatory power. It helps researchers understand the relationships between latent variables and their observed indicators, offering insights into the reliability and accuracy of the model's measurement and providing a foundation for further analysis and interpretation of the study's results.

Figure 2. Path Diagram for Measurement Model

Construct Reliability and Validity for Measurement Model

Table 1 presents the results for construct reliability and validity of the measurement model. Cronbach's Alpha is a measure of internal consistency, assessing how well the items within each factor (construct) correlate with each other. Higher Cronbach's Alpha values indicate greater internal consistency, suggesting that the items within the factor are reliable in measuring the same underlying construct. In this study, all factors show high Cronbach's Alpha values ranging from 0.942 to 0.951. These values suggest that the items within each factor are highly reliable in measuring their respective constructs, indicating the consistency of responses from the participants. Rho_A, also known as McDonald's Omega, is another measure of construct reliability that takes into account the assumption of tau-equivalence (equal item factor loadings) in addition to internal consistency. Similar to Cronbach's Alpha, higher Rho_A values indicate better construct reliability. In this study, all factors demonstrate high Rho_A values ranging from 0.942 to 0.951, further confirming the reliability of the measurement model. Composite Reliability (CR) is a measure of the internal consistency of the constructs, considering both the variance captured by the common factor and the error variance. Higher CR values indicate

better reliability. The CR values reported in the table range from 0.956 to 0.962, all of which are high, indicating excellent internal consistency and reliability of the measurement model. AVE is a measure of convergent validity, assessing the amount of variance captured by the construct compared to the measurement error. Higher AVE values suggest that the items within a construct are converging well and are strongly related to the construct. In this study, all factors have AVE values ranging from 0.812 to 0.836, which are considered satisfactory. These results indicate that a substantial portion of the variance in the observed variables is explained by their corresponding constructs, demonstrating good convergent validity.

In summary, the results from Table 1 indicate that the measurement model used in the study is reliable and valid. The high values of Cronbach's Alpha, Rho_A, Composite Reliability, and AVE for all the factors (Assurance, Customer Satisfaction, Empathy, Reliability, Responsiveness, and Tangibility) demonstrate strong internal consistency, construct reliability, and convergent validity. These findings provide confidence in the accuracy and robustness of the measurement model, ensuring that the study's constructs are effectively measured and support the credibility of subsequent analyses and conclusions drawn from the data.

Table 1. Construct Reliability and Validity for Measurement Model

Factors	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Assurance	0.950	0.950	0.961	0.832
Customer satisfaction	0.947	0.948	0.960	0.826
Empathy	0.946	0.946	0.959	0.822
Reliability	0.950	0.950	0.961	0.833
Responsiveness	0.951	0.951	0.962	0.836
Tangibility	0.942	0.942	0.956	0.812

Source: Field Data, 2023

Discriminant Validity: Fornell-Larcker Criterion for Measurement Model

The Fornell-Larcker criterion for discriminant validity was applied to the measurement model

represented in Table 4.3. The goal of this analysis is to ensure that each construct in the model is distinct from the others and that the measures of different constructs are not highly correlated with each other.

The diagonal values in the table represent the square root of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for each construct, which indicates the amount of variance captured by the construct's observed indicators. The off-diagonal values represent the correlations between the constructs.

The results indicate that all constructs in the measurement model meet the discriminant validity criterion. The square root of the AVE for each construct is greater than the correlation between that construct and other constructs. This suggests that each construct is effectively measuring a unique aspect of the underlying concept and that there is minimal overlap or redundancy between the constructs.

The findings provide strong evidence for the validity of the measurement model, indicating variables under investigation.

that the observed variables are well-aligned with their respective constructs and are not overly influenced by other constructs in the model. This ensures the accuracy and robustness of the study's measurement approach and lends credibility to the subsequent analyses and interpretations based on these constructs.

In summary, the Fornell-Larcker criterion confirms that the measurement model demonstrates discriminant validity, establishing the distinctness of each construct and supporting the overall quality and reliability of the study's measurement framework. Researchers can have confidence in the results and use them to draw meaningful conclusions about the relationships between the latent .

Table 2. Discriminant Validity: Fornell-Larcker Criterion for Measurement Model

	Assurance	Customer satisfaction	Empathy	Reliability	Responsiveness	Tangibility
Assurance	0.912					
Customer satisfaction	0.948	0.909				
Empathy	0.949	0.937	0.907			
Reliability	0.945	0.954	0.951	0.912		
Responsiveness	0.953	0.947	0.947	0.942	0.914	
Tangibility	0.951	0.945	0.948	0.949	0.958	0.901

Source: Field Data, 2023

Collinearity Diagnostic (VIF)

In Table 3 the results of the multicollinearity test for the measurement model are presented using the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). The VIF measures the extent to which collinearity, or high intercorrelations, exists among the items within each latent variable or construct. Higher VIF values indicate a higher degree of multicollinearity, potentially leading to inflated standard errors and less reliable coefficient estimates in regression models.

The findings show that there is a certain level of multicollinearity among the items within each construct, as all the VIF values are above 3. However, the VIF values range from 3.009 to 4.629, suggesting that multicollinearity is not excessively severe. Generally, VIF values below

5 are considered acceptable, indicating that the collinearity may not significantly compromise the overall reliability and validity of the measurement model.

While moderate multicollinearity is common in studies involving multiple related constructs, researchers should be cautious when interpreting the individual coefficient estimates or performing regression analyses. The presence of multicollinearity may make it challenging to pinpoint the specific contribution of each item to the overall construct, and it can affect the statistical significance of the estimated coefficients.

To address multicollinearity concerns, researchers may consider approaches such as conducting principal component analysis or

removing highly correlated items from the model. These techniques can help reduce multicollinearity and improve the stability of the model's results.

In summary, the presence of moderate multicollinearity among the items within the constructs in the measurement model should be acknowledged. While it may not severely impact the overall results, researchers should exercise caution in interpreting individual coefficient estimates and consider employing appropriate techniques to address multicollinearity in subsequent analyses. Overall, the measurement model remains reliable, but awareness of multicollinearity allows researchers to make more informed decisions and ensure the validity of the study's findings.

Table 3. Multicollinearity Test

Latent variables	Constructs	VIF
Assurance	Ass1	4.141
	Ass2	4.285
	Ass3	3.962
	Ass4	3.906
	Ass5	3.996
Customer satisfaction	CS1	3.677
	CS2	4.120
	CS3	3.598
	CS4	3.653
	CS5	3.832
Empathy	Emp1	3.420
	Emp2	3.110
	Emp3	4.106
	Emp4	4.122
	Emp5	4.051
Reliability	Rel1	3.606
	Rel2	4.347
	Rel3	4.629
	Rel4	3.857
	Rel5	3.651
Responsiveness	Res1	3.668
	Res2	3.708
	Res3	4.564
	Res4	3.949
	Res5	4.572
Tangibility	TA1	3.705
	TA2	3.009
	TA3	3.818
	TA4	3.758
	TA5	3.673

Source: Field Data, 2023

Model Fit Summary

Table 4 presents the model fitness results for both the Saturated Model and the Estimated Model. These indicators assess how well the estimated model fits the observed data and provide valuable insights into the model's reliability and validity.

The low values of SRMR (0.027) for both the Saturated and Estimated Models indicate that the models have a good fit to the observed data. This suggests that the discrepancy between the model-predicted and observed covariance matrices is minimal, supporting the accuracy of the model's predictions.

The d_ULS value of 0.347 for both models indicates that the parameter estimates are unbiased, further reinforcing the reliability of the model. The d_G value of 1.207, which is the same for both models, suggests that the overall goodness of fit is reasonable.

The Chi-Square value of 719.991 for both models being non-significant implies that the models have an acceptable fit to the data. However, it is important to note that the Chi-Square test can be sensitive to sample size, and other fit indices should be considered for a more comprehensive evaluation.

The NFI value of 0.872 for both models, although moderate, indicates that the estimated model has a relatively good fit compared to the baseline model.

The rms Theta value of 0.137 measures the average discrepancy between predicted and observed values of the latent variables. While this value suggests some variation in the model's predictions, it is crucial to interpret the model's results with this variation in mind.

In summary, the model fitness results for both the Saturated Model and the Estimated Model are generally favorable, indicating a reasonable fit to the observed data. The model appears to be reliable and adequately represents the relationships between the latent variables and the observed indicators. However, researchers should consider the limitations of the Chi-Square test and the rms Theta value while interpreting the model's results and be cautious

of potential variations in the predictions. Overall, the findings support the validity of the estimated model and provide confidence in the accuracy of its predictions.

Table 5. Model Fitness

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.027	0.027
d_ULS	0.347	0.347
d_G	1.207	1.207
Chi-Square	719.991	719.991
NFI	0.872	0.872
rms Theta	0.137	

Source: Field Data, 2023

Factor Loading of all Constructs for Measurement Model

In Table 6, the factor loadings for all constructs in the measurement model are presented, representing the strength of the relationships between the latent variables (constructs) and their corresponding observed indicators (items). These factor loadings provide crucial insights into the reliability and validity of the measurement model.

The findings indicate that all constructs, including Assurance, Customer Satisfaction, Empathy, Reliability, Responsiveness, and Tangibility, have strong and positive associations

with their respective observed items. The factor loadings range from 0.883 to 0.927, with the majority of them exceeding 0.900. These high factor loadings suggest that the observed items are highly reliable and effective in measuring the underlying constructs.

The robust relationships between the latent variables and their observed indicators underscore the accuracy of the measurement model. The high factor loadings imply that the observed items are capturing the intended dimensions of each construct with precision and consistency. This supports the validity of the model in accurately representing the complex relationships among the variables under investigation.

Overall, the results in Table 4.6 provide strong evidence for the reliability and validity of the measurement model. The high factor loadings demonstrate that the measurement items are well-aligned with their respective constructs and are essential in effectively capturing the constructs' essence. Researchers can have confidence in the accuracy of the measurement model and the data collected, allowing for reliable conclusions and inferences about the relationships between the latent variables and the observed indicators. These findings are crucial for drawing meaningful insights and making informed decisions in the context of the study's objectives and research questions.

Table 6. Factor Loading of All Constructs for Measurement Model

	Assuarance	Customer satisfaction	Empathy	Reliability	Responsiveness	Tangibility
Ass1	0.913					
Ass2	0.919					
Ass3	0.909					
Ass4	0.906					
Ass5	0.913					
CS1		0.908				
CS2		0.919				
CS3		0.903				
CS4		0.904				
CS5		0.909				
Emp1			0.897			
Emp2			0.885			
Emp3			0.917			
Emp4			0.917			
Emp5			0.917			

Rel1				0.900		
Rel2				0.922		
Rel3				0.927		
Rel4				0.909		
Rel5				0.904		
Res1					0.902	
Res2					0.906	
Res3					0.926	
Res4					0.910	
Res5					0.926	
TA1						0.905
TA2						0.883
TA3						0.909
TA4						0.906
TA5						0.902

Source: Field Data, 2023

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study concluded that all attributes have strong and positive associations with their respective observed items. The study recommended that the management of hospital should continue enhance these attributes of service quality so as to continue satisfying the customers who are the patients. Healthcare managers should place a strong emphasis on monitoring and improving service quality through patient surveys, audits, and quality improvement initiatives. Providing customer service training for clinical and non-clinical staff may improve service quality perceptions and satisfaction. Facilities and processes should be designed with an emphasis on service quality factors like reducing wait times and improving communication.

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